

Synergistic targeting of the HIF-1 α /autophagy axis sensitizes hypoxic MCF-7 breast cancer cells to apoptosis via PTEN upregulation and Bcl-2 collapse

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Received 8 March 2026 ♦ Accepted 9 May 2026 ♦ Published 21 May 2026

Citation: Al-Mashhadani Z, Arif IS (2026) Synergistic targeting of the HIF-1 α /autophagy axis sensitizes hypoxic MCF-7 breast cancer cells to apoptosis via PTEN upregulation and Bcl-2 collapse. *Pharmacia* 73: e190219. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e190219>

Abstract

This study investigates the synergistic potential of combining the repurposed autophagy inhibitor tioconazole with the HIF-1 α inhibitor PX-478 or the proteasome inhibitor bortezomib in hypoxic MCF-7 cells. Hydralazine was used to induce cellular hypoxia chemically. An MTT assay was used to assess cell viability. Synergism was examined using the SynergyFinder web-based software, while metastatic potential was assessed using wound-healing assays. RT-qPCR and Western blotting experiments were used to quantify the expression of hypoxia, autophagy, and survival markers (HIF-1 α , BNIP3, ATG7, PTEN, Beclin-1, and Bcl-2). Tioconazole exhibited broad-range synergistic cytotoxicity (synergy score > 10) and significantly inhibited cell migration ($p < 0.01$) when combined with PX-478 or bortezomib. While monotherapies retained elevated HIF-1 α mRNA levels compared to the control, combination treatments caused substantial suppression of HIF-1 α protein, indicating post-transcriptional degradation. Importantly, the PX-478/tioconazole combination significantly upregulated the tumor suppressor PTEN (2.27-fold, $p < 0.01$), exceeding the bortezomib combination, and markedly reversed monotherapy-induced anti-apoptotic Bcl-2 expression while preserving Beclin-1 suppression. These findings introduce a promising treatment approach for overcoming complex adaptive resistance pathways by repurposing tioconazole in combination with the selective HIF-1 α inhibitor PX-478 in hypoxic breast cancer cells.

Keywords

Bcl-2, bortezomib, cancer hypoxia, hydralazine, PTEN, PX-478, repurposed drug, tioconazole

Introduction

Breast cancer persists as a major worldwide health concern, characterized by substantial metabolic adaptability, enabling cancerous cells to develop and survive in stressful microenvironments (Siegel et al. 2024; A-Qader et al. 2025; Salih et al. 2025). A key factor in this adaptation is hypoxia, a characteristic of solid tumors caused

by abnormal vascularization and rapid cellular growth (Zhi et al. 2024). Under these oxygen-limited conditions, hypoxia-inducible factor 1 alpha (HIF-1 α) stabilization integrates a transcriptional pathway promoting glycolytic metabolism, angiogenesis, and tolerance to apoptosis (Missiaen et al. 2023). Importantly, recent findings reveal a functional link between HIF-1 α stability and autophagy, a fundamental catabolic system that degrades protein aggregates

gates and malfunctioning organelles to maintain cellular homeostasis (Zaarour et al. 2021; Raza et al. 2024; Jalouli 2025; Chen et al. 2026). Although autophagy can serve as a tumor suppressor during early malignancies, it often has a cytoprotective impact on established tumor development, allowing cancer cells to tolerate metabolic stress and chemotherapy interventions (Hassan et al. 2024).

The regulation of autophagy by HIF-1 α occurs via certain molecular mediators, such as BNIP3 (Bcl-2/adenovirus E1B 19 kDa-interacting protein 3), ATG7, and Beclin-1, facilitating breast cancer cell survival in hypoxic environments (Huang et al. 2025; Jalouli 2025). As a consequence, pharmacological inhibition of the HIF-1 α /autophagy pathway represents a promising therapeutic approach. To systematically examine this axis, it is essential to employ agents that target different functional sites within this complicated signaling network.

Regarding the experimental compounds that target hypoxia signaling, PX-478 has emerged as an effective, orally bioavailable small-molecule inhibitor that selectively represses the constitutive expression of HIF-1 α . In contrast to other drugs that only affect hypoxia signaling indirectly, PX-478 directly reduces the level of HIF-1 α protein in both normoxic and hypoxic microenvironments by reducing its transcription and translation and facilitating its destruction (Liu et al. 2024). As a result of its demonstrated efficacy in inhibiting tumor development in preclinical models of different solid cancers and advancing to clinical investigation, PX-478 represents a highly relevant and reliable strategy for evaluating direct upstream hypoxic suppression (Zhu et al. 2017; Jalouli 2025).

Conversely, bortezomib, an FDA-approved proteasome inhibitor frequently employed for multiple myeloma, exerts a completely distinct pharmacological strategy. Even though bortezomib inhibits the proteasomal breakdown of proteins, including HIF-1 α and Beclin-1, it interestingly makes the impeded protein transcriptionally inactive, which possibly disturbs the hypoxia response and modifies the autophagic mechanisms via the accumulation of misfolded proteins and induction of severe endoplasmic reticulum stress (Befani et al. 2012; Sun et al. 2015; Zafeiropoulou et al. 2024). This dual function makes bortezomib an attractive candidate to evaluate indirect and stress-associated interactions with the HIF-1 α /autophagy axis. However, this drug displays increased drug resistance as monotherapy in clinical trials for treating breast cancer, possibly due to activation of autophagy through stabilizing ATF4 and increasing LC3B (Milani et al. 2009; Zafeiropoulou et al. 2024). Interestingly, a lower dose of bortezomib in a preclinical study showed another pathway to inhibit HIF-1 α activation through stimulation of factor inhibiting HIF-1 (FIH-1), which converts active HIF-1 α into an inactive form (Shin et al. 2008). This inhibition opens the possibility of using a lower dose of bortezomib instead of the regular dose to avoid drug resistance by preventing autophagy and breast cancer cell survival.

To accurately assess the potential therapeutic efficacy of targeting the autophagy mechanism, it is essential to

compare the previously mentioned agents to direct modulators of this pathway. Repurposing currently available non-cancer medications is a rapidly developing method in cancer treatment, since they have well-documented safety profiles (Weng et al. 2023; Xia et al. 2024). Tioconazole, an azole antifungal, has been repurposed as an effective blocker of ATG4B, a cysteine protease necessary for the production of autophagosomes (Liu et al. 2018). In contrast to upstream regulators, tioconazole specifically inhibits LC3 cleavage, providing a unique pathway to suppress autophagy (Liu et al. 2018).

The rational selection of these three compounds results in an attractive comparative model. A comparative investigation of direct upstream transcriptional repression of hypoxia (PX-478), indirect proteasomal disruption (bortezomib), and direct downstream autophagy inhibition (tioconazole) is crucial for determining efficient approaches to prevent stress-induced survival pathways in breast cancer cells.

Materials and methods

Chemicals

Penicillin, streptomycin, Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium (DMEM), phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), fetal bovine serum (FBS), and trypsin were obtained from Capricorn Scientific (Germany). Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was purchased from Euroclone (Italy). Cell culture flasks and plates used in this study were provided by Nest-Biotechnology (China). MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) and crystal violet powders were purchased from Promega (USA). PX-478, bortezomib, and tioconazole were provided by MedChemExpress (NJ, USA). Hydralazine was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich/Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany). HIF-1 α polyclonal antibody (catalog no.: FNab09940) was obtained from FineTest (China), while GAPDH (catalog no.: E-AB-40337), Beclin-1 (catalog no.: E-AB-53242), and Bcl-2 (catalog no.: E-AB-60012) polyclonal antibodies were purchased from Elabscience (Houston, USA). Horseradish peroxidase (HRP)-conjugated secondary antibodies (catalog no.: E-AB-1003) were obtained from Elabscience (Houston, USA). All compounds were dissolved in suitable solvents to prepare stock solutions and sterilized by filtration through a 0.22 μ m Millipore syringe filter, then stored at -20°C . Working solutions were prepared immediately before experiments by mixing complete culture medium with a suitable volume of stock solution.

Cell culture and maintenance

The human breast cancer cell line MCF-7 was obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC; Manassas, VA, USA). Cells were regularly cultured in DMEM complemented with 10% FBS and 1% penicillin-streptomycin antibiotic solution. The incubation

environment was maintained at 37 °C in 98% humidity with a 5% CO₂ atmosphere. Regular passages were performed using 0.05% trypsin when cells reached 70–80% confluence. Cells were routinely tested for bacterial and mycoplasma infections. For hypoxia induction, cells were exposed to 100 μM hydralazine for 6 h to increase HIF-1α production, then treated with the tested chemicals for the designated time periods. To minimize vehicle toxicity, the final DMSO concentration was kept below 0.1% (v/v) in culture media.

In vitro cell cytotoxicity assay

The cytotoxic effects of compounds were assessed using the MTT assay (Ghasemi et al. 2021; Naser et al. 2025). In 96-well plates, MCF-7 cells were seeded at a density of 5×10^3 cells/well. The next day, the cells were treated with a consistent range of concentrations of bortezomib (2.5–1280 nM), PX-478 (2.5–1280 μM), and tioconazole (2.5–1280 μM) at 24, 48, and 72 h. In the control group, only DMEM supplemented with an equal percentage of solvent was added to the cells. The final concentration of DMSO was maintained below 0.1% across all treatments that used it as a vehicle solvent. After a certain incubation time, the medium was removed, and fresh media containing MTT solution (0.5 mg/mL) were added to each well. Plates were then covered with foil and incubated for 4 h at 37 °C and 5% CO₂ to form formazan crystals by metabolically active cells. After the incubation period was completed, the culture media were discarded, and 100 μL of DMSO was added with shaking for 10 min to dissolve the crystals formed. The optical density (OD) for each well was measured using a GloMax Microplate Reader (Promega, USA) at 560 and 600 nm. Cell viability was presented as a percentage of the untreated control, and half-maximum inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) values were determined using nonlinear regression analysis. Cell viability was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Cell viability \%} = [\text{OD sample}/\text{OD control}] \times 100.$$

Drug interaction and synergy analysis

To evaluate the potential combination effect of HIF-1α inhibitors and autophagy modulators, synergy scores were obtained using the SynergyFinder web software (Ianevski et al. 2022). The concentrations of the drug combination (PX-478/tioconazole or bortezomib/tioconazole) used in this method were based on the IC₅₀ calculated from the previously mentioned cell viability assay. MCF-7 cells were treated with several concentrations (1/4 IC₅₀, 1/2 IC₅₀, IC₅₀, two IC₅₀S, and four IC₅₀ S) of each drug or combination using the logarithmic method. Reference system, zero interaction potency (ZIP) was used to quantify the degree of interaction. Synergy scores > 10, between 10 and –10, and < –10 were indicated as synergistic, additive, and antagonistic, respectively.

Wound healing migration assay

The *in vitro* scratch assay protocol was used to assess cell migration (Kauanova et al. 2021). In 24-well plates, MCF-7 cells were seeded at a density of 1×10^5 cells/well and cultured until a confluent monolayer was formed. Using a sterile 200 μL pipette tip, a straight linear scratch was performed in the cell monolayer. Floating cells from the scratching process were removed by washing with pre-warmed PBS solution, and fresh media containing the examined agent concentrations were added. The 0-h image of the wound area was captured immediately, then images at 24, 48, and 72 h post-wounding were captured using an inverted phase-contrast microscope (Optica®, Italy) at 40× magnification. Images were taken using live-cell imaging at each designed time point. The migration rates were measured by quantifying the reduction in wound area using ImageJ software, where the data were calculated as the percentage of wound closure compared to the initial starting time using the following formula:

$$\text{Wound closure } 100\% = (A_0 - A_t / A_0) \times 100,$$

where A₀ represents the initial wound area at time zero, and A_t represents the wound area measured at the specific time points.

Quantitative real-time PCR (RT-qPCR)

MCF-7 cells were seeded in 6-well plates and treated with 100 μM hydralazine for 6 h to induce hypoxia, then treated with the examined agents for 48 h. Total RNA was then extracted using the GENEzol TriRNA Pure Kit (Geneaid, New Taipei City, Taiwan) according to the manufacturer's protocol. The NanoDrop Microvolume Spectrophotometer was used to quantify the extracted RNA. Using the QIAGEN Rotor-Gene Q RT-PCR System (Germany), first-strand cDNA was created from the total RNA mixture. Quantitative real-time polymerase chain reaction amplification was performed using the SYBR Green Master Mix (Tinzyme Co., Limited, Guangdong, China). The experiment was carried out using the qTOWER³ G instrument (Analytik-Jena, Germany), programmed for 40 cycles of 15 s at 95 °C and 30 s at 60 °C for annealing and 20 min for melting curves. The expression levels of HIF-1α, BNIP3, PTEN, and ATG7 genes were quantified and analyzed using the 2^{-ΔΔCt} method, and the results were normalized to GAPDH as a housekeeping gene (Al-Hamdy et al. 2025). Primer sequences were designed using the PrimerQuest Tool (Integrated DNA Technologies, Coralville, IA, USA) and purchased from Macrogen.co, South Korea (Table 1).

Western blotting assay

MCF-7 cells were seeded at a density of 2×10^5 cells/well using 6-well plates and treated with 100 μM hydralazine for 6 h to induce hypoxia, then treated with the examined agents. After 48 h of treatment, cells were

Table 1. Primer oligonucleotides used for quantitative PCR (qPCR).

Target Gene	Forward (5' → 3')	Reverse (5' → 3')
GAPDH	GGTGTGAACCATGAGAAGTATGA	GAGTCCTTCCACGATACCAAAG
HIF-1 α	GTCTGCAACATGGAAGGTATTG	GCAGGTCATAGTGGTTTCT
BNIP3	CATGAGGAACACGAGCGTCA	GTGCTGGTGGAGGTTGTCA
PTEN	AAGGGACGAACTGGTGTAATG	GCCTCTGACTGGGAATAGTTAC
ATG7	CCTGAACAGATGGACAGTTGC	GTTGAGGACGTTGGTGTGTC

lysed, and total protein was extracted using cold RIPA lysis buffer containing protease and phosphatase inhibitors. Protein concentrations were measured using the bicinchoninic acid (BCA) assay. Protein was then separated using the sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) method and transferred onto a polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) membrane. After the transfer process, PVDF membranes were blocked with skimmed milk at room temperature and then incubated overnight at 4 °C with primary antibodies against HIF-1 α (dilution ratio 1:2000), Beclin-1 (dilution ratio 1:1000), or Bcl-2 (dilution ratio 1:1000), as well as GAPDH (dilution ratio 1:5000) as a loading control. The next day, PVDF membranes were incubated with suitable horseradish peroxidase (HRP)-conjugated secondary antibodies (dilution ratio 1:5000) for 1 h, and protein bands were then detected using a chemiluminescence detection assay via a ChemiDoc imaging system, Bio-Rad (USA). Band density was quantified using ImageJ analysis software and normalized against the loading control (Sule et al. 2023).

Statistical analysis

GraphPad Prism (version 8.0.2, GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA, USA) was used to perform statistical analysis. The mean \pm standard deviation (SD) was used to express the results data. Statistical comparisons among groups were performed using one-way or two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's post-test for multiple comparisons. Nonlinear regression was used to assess the IC₅₀ values. Differences with a *p*-value less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Results

Dose-response analysis of HIF-1 α and autophagy inhibitors

Cell viability was measured using the MTT assay to determine the baseline sensitivity of MCF-7 cells to the examined agents. All three drugs exhibited a dose-dependent repression in cell viability, with IC₅₀ values of approximately 109, 10, and 8.9 μ M for PX-478; 45.5, 20, and 15 nM for bortezomib; and 101, 41, and 20 μ M for tioconazole at 24, 48, and 72 h time intervals, respectively (Fig. 1). The middle values at 48 h were selected as the reference points for subsequent combination assays.

Synergistic interaction between HIF-1 α inhibitors and tioconazole

To evaluate the efficacy enhancement of HIF-1 α inhibitors by a direct autophagy blocker, synergy effects were examined using the SynergyFinder software. The combination of tioconazole with PX-478 showed extensive synergism (synergy score > 10) over a wide range of concentrations (Fig. 2). In particular, synergistic effects were displayed at the following mix pairs of PX-478/tioconazole (μ M): 10/10.5, 10/84, 20/10.5, 20/21, 20/42, 20/84, 40/21, and 40/42. However, the remaining mix pairs showed an additive effect (< 10 to > -10), with no antagonism (Fig. 2; Suppl. material 1: table S1). In contrast, there was a smaller window of synergism in the combination of bortezomib and tioconazole. Substantial synergistic values (> 10) were limited to higher concentrations of tioconazole paired with varied dosages of bortezomib (bortezomib/tioconazole ratios of 10/82, 20/82, 40/82, and 80/82, where the bortezomib dose is in nM and tioconazole is in μ M). Lower concentrations of the bortezomib/tioconazole combination produced additive or indifferent effects (Fig. 2; Suppl. material 1: table S1), suggesting that the potentiation of bortezomib toxicity in MCF-7 cells is conditional on establishing a threshold blockage of autophagy.

Impairment of cell migration

The metastatic capacity of MCF-7 cells was assessed using a wound-healing experiment. Under control (normoxic) and hydralazine-induced hypoxic settings, cells migrated freely and almost closed wounds after 72 h (Fig. 3). Treatment with monotherapy (PX-478, bortezomib, or tioconazole) produced a significant decline in migration rates relative to the hydralazine group. However, the combination groups demonstrated the most profound reduction in motility. Both PX-478 + tioconazole (*p* < 0.001) and bortezomib + tioconazole (*p* < 0.01) interventions effectively delayed migration, leading to a significantly larger wound gap than single treatment, demonstrating that disrupting hypoxia signaling and autophagy together can impair cellular motility (Fig. 3).

Modulation of hypoxic and autophagic gene expression (RT-qPCR)

The analysis of gene expression showed particular regulatory patterns in response to both hydralazine and pharmacological treatments (Fig. 4). In comparison to the untreated control group, the chemical hypoxia model with

Figure 1. Dose–response curves and IC₅₀ of PX-478, bortezomib, and tioconazole on MCF-7 cells. Confluent cultures of MCF-7 cells were treated with increasing concentrations of (A) PX-478 (2.5–1280 μM), (B) bortezomib (2.5–1280 nM), or (C) tioconazole (2.5–1280 μM) for 24, 48, and 72 h. The MTT assay was used to determine the viability of the cells. The final concentration of DMSO was maintained below 0.1% in the control group and all treatments that used it as a vehicle solvent. The data are displayed as mean ± SD. *N* = 6.

hydralazine efficiently induced a hypoxic and autophagic transcriptional response, doubling the mRNA levels of HIF-1α, BNIP3, and ATG7 ($p < 0.05$), confirming the activation of compensatory survival systems under hypoxic stress. The level of the tumor suppressor gene PTEN was marginally decreased (0.93-fold), as shown in Fig. 4. Interestingly, treatment with PX-478 as a monotherapy reversed the upregulation of HIF-1α, BNIP3, and ATG7 ($p < 0.05$) induced by hydralazine, which reduced the examined mRNA to approximately baseline control levels. However, bortezomib treatment at different doses produced persistent transcriptional activation, with the same effect as the hypoxia-hydralazine group on the expression of HIF-1α and a lower level on BNIP3 and ATG7 but still higher than baseline control levels (Fig. 4A–C).

In response to downstream autophagy inhibition, tioconazole monotherapy caused a significant reduction in ATG7 mRNA levels ($p < 0.05$) compared to the hypoxia group and additive overexpression of BNIP3 (approximately 3.5-fold, $p < 0.05$), most likely indicating a feedback mechanism for autophagy blockage (Fig. 4B, C). However, the addition of tioconazole to the HIF-1α and proteasome inhibitors altered their transcriptional effects. The combination regimens modestly decreased HIF-1α and ATG7 expression (PX-478 + tioconazole = 1.15-fold and 1.23-fold; bortezomib + tioconazole = 1.59-fold and 1.45-fold, respectively), while maintaining high expression of BNIP3 (PX-478 + tioconazole = 2.12-fold; bortezomib + tioconazole = 3-fold), when compared to the hydralazine group (Fig. 4A–C).

The most substantial transcriptional alteration was observed with PTEN. Although monotherapies produced

mild to moderate PTEN upregulation (PX-478 = 1.77-fold [$p < 0.05$], bortezomib 20 nM = 1.07-fold, bortezomib 1 nM = 1.12-fold, and tioconazole = 1.25-fold), the PX-478 + tioconazole combination generated a substantial 2.27-fold increase ($p < 0.01$) in PTEN mRNA levels. This synergistic restoration was considerably superior to the bortezomib/tioconazole combination (1.29-fold), demonstrating an evident transcriptional mechanism for how the PX-478 and tioconazole combination effectively disrupts hypoxia survival signals (Fig. 4D).

Impact on protein expression (Western blot)

The results of protein expression validated the disruption of survival pathways (Fig. 5). In the hypoxia-hydralazine group, the levels of HIF-1α, Beclin-1, and Bcl-2 proteins were marginally elevated compared to the control. In relation to HIF-1α, both PX-478 and bortezomib monotherapies caused a 0.5-fold reduction ($p < 0.001$) in protein levels compared to hydralazine treatment (Fig. 5B). Interestingly, treatment with tioconazole alone showed a significant reduction ($p < 0.01$) in HIF-1α protein, with a level slightly higher than treatment with other drugs. However, HIF-1α stability further collapsed when tioconazole was combined with PX-478 or bortezomib, lowering levels to approximately 0.25-fold ($p < 0.0001$) of the hypoxia group (Fig. 5B). On the other hand, Beclin-1 levels were effectively reduced by PX-478 (~0.9-fold) and tioconazole (~0.6-fold, $p < 0.05$) mono-treatments compared to the hydralazine group (Fig. 5C). Remarkably,

Figure 3. Inhibition of MCF-7 cell migration by combination targeting of HIF-1 α and autophagy. **(A)** Phase-contrast images of wound-healing experiments. Confluent monolayers of MCF-7 cells were scratched, and wound closure was monitored at 0 h and 72 h post-treatment. Dashed lines represent the wound margins. **(B)** Quantification analysis of cell migration expressed as the percentage of wound closure relative to the initial gap width. The combination of PX-478 and tioconazole showed the most significant retention of the wound gap. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD. The final concentration of DMSO was maintained below 0.1% in the control group and all treatments that used it as a vehicle solvent. Statistical significance was determined using one-way ANOVA relative to the control group (* p < 0.01, ** p < 0.001, and *** p < 0.001) and the hydralazine group (# p < 0.05, ## p < 0.01, and ### p < 0.001). HDZ = hydralazine, PX = PX-478, BZM1 (B1) = bortezomib 1 nM, BZM20 (B20) = bortezomib 20 nM, Tio (T) = tioconazole. N = 3.

Figure 4. RT-qPCR analysis of hypoxia and autophagy downstream genes. Kinetics of gene expression were measured in MCF-7 cells treated with hydralazine in addition to PX-478, bortezomib, tioconazole, or their combination for 48 h. Gene expression of (A) HIF-1 α , (B) BNIP3, (C) ATG7, and (D) PTEN was normalized relative to the expression of the housekeeping gene GAPDH. Data are presented as mean \pm SD and analyzed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-test. The final concentration of DMSO was maintained below 0.1% in the control group and all treatments that used it as a vehicle solvent. * $p < 0.01$ and ** $p < 0.001$ vs. control, while # $p < 0.05$ vs. the hydralazine (hypoxic) group. HDZ = hydralazine, PX = PX-478, BZM1 (B1) = bortezomib 1 nM, BZM20 (B20) = bortezomib 20 nM, Tio (T) = tioconazole, $N = 3$.

the tioconazole + PX-478 combination lowered Beclin-1 to approximately 0.7-fold, but bortezomib doses alone or in combination preserved Beclin-1 protein at almost the same level as the hypoxia group.

The anti-apoptotic marker Bcl-2 was paradoxically elevated by single-agent treatments (PX-478: ~ 2.5 -fold, $p < 0.01$; bortezomib 20 nM: ~ 3 -fold, $p < 0.001$; bortezomib 1 nM: ~ 1.7 -fold; tioconazole: ~ 2.3 -fold, $p < 0.01$) compared to the hydralazine group, indicating a compensatory survival strategy under HIF-1 α or autophagy-blocking stress (Fig. 5D). Importantly, this response was effectively prevented by combining PX-478 and tioconazole, which significantly decreased Bcl-2 levels to 0.7 times ($p < 0.001$) compared to each agent alone. In contrast, the tioconazole/bortezomib combination presented a partial reduction in Bcl-2 levels compared to monotherapy, indicating that the tioconazole/PX-478 regimen is superior in overcoming apoptotic resistance (Fig. 5D).

Discussion

The metabolic adaptability of breast cancer cells, including their ability to stabilize HIF-1 α and utilize the benefits of cytoprotective autophagy in hypoxic environments, remains a challenge in finding effective therapies (Wang et al. 2024). For assessing new chemotherapies in preclinical studies, it is essential to model this crucial hypoxic environment using a hypoxia-mimicking *in vitro* model. Hydralazine has been shown to induce hypoxia in normal brain cells by directly activating the HIF-1 α pathway through inhibiting prolyl hydroxylase domain (PHD) enzyme activity, which is responsible for HIF-1 α degradation (Chatard et al. 2017). Using this agent in tumor environments as a hypoxia inducer has previously been validated in MCF-7 breast cancer cells (Al-Mashhadani and Arif 2026). In this study, hydralazine was used as a hypoxia-mimetic agent to examine the therapeutic effectiveness of

Figure 5. Representative Western blots for different proteins and corresponding densitograms. Confluent cultures of MCF-7 cells were dosed with 100 μ M hydralazine and incubated for 6 h. Cells were then treated with PX-478, bortezomib, tioconazole, or their combination. (A) After 48 h, protein extraction and separation were performed using a Western blotting assay. GAPDH was used as a loading control to ensure equal protein loading. The relative fold expression of (B) HIF-1 α , (C) Beclin-1, and (D) Bcl-2 proteins was measured compared to the untreated control (Cont.). Data are presented as mean \pm SD and analyzed using two-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-test. The final concentration of DMSO was maintained below 0.1% in the control group and all treatments that used it as a vehicle solvent. ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001, and **** p < 0.0001 vs. control, while # p < 0.05, ## p < 0.01, ### p < 0.001, and #### p < 0.0001 vs. the hydralazine (hypoxic) group. \$ p < 0.05, \$\$ p < 0.01, and \$\$\$ p < 0.001 vs. the indicated group. HDZ = hydralazine, PX = PX-478, BZM1 (B1) = bortezomib 1 nM, BZM20 (B20) = bortezomib 20 nM, Tio (T) = tioconazole, N = 3.

targeting HIF-1 α with PX-478, the proteasome with bortezomib, and autophagy with tioconazole in MCF-7 cells. Hydralazine has been shown to induce hypoxia *in vitro* by directly activating the HIF-1 pathway by inhibiting PHD activity. The findings show that combining the autophagy inhibitor tioconazole with either PX-478 or bortezomib produces considerable synergistic cytotoxicity, restricts cell migration, and profoundly compromises hypoxic adaptation networks in MCF-7 breast cancer cells. This is consistent with recent practical research showing that monotherapies affecting a single-response axis usually fail due to the rapid activation of adaptive survival pathways, whereas appropriate simultaneous blockade methods can trigger a destructive metabolic collapse in solid tumors (Wang et al. 2023; Waks et al. 2024).

Following hydralazine treatment, HIF-1 α and its downstream markers BNIP3 and ATG7 showed considerable upregulation, confirming the validity of using this agent as a hypoxic model (Fig. 4). This reflects the transcriptional pattern of solid tumors, where HIF-1 α acts as an essential regulator of metabolic adaptability (Yong et al. 2022; Ba-

sheeruddin and Qausain 2024; Zhi et al. 2024). In relation to the HIF-1 α inhibitors, the results of this study demonstrated different molecular patterns. PX-478 exhibited a characteristic inhibitory effect, lowering HIF-1 α mRNA and protein levels (Figs 4A, 5A, B), which is compatible with its role in inhibiting constitutive and hypoxia-induced HIF-1 α translation (Zhu et al. 2017; Panahi Meymandi et al. 2024). In contrast, bortezomib exhibited a complicated regulatory pattern. It effectively lowered HIF-1 α protein levels (0.5-fold), while the expression of HIF-1 α mRNA remained elevated (~2-fold), as shown in Figs 4A, 5A, B. Although bortezomib predominantly represents a proteasomal inhibitor, recent evidence demonstrates that it can restrict HIF-1 α production by inhibiting the PI3K/Akt/mTOR complex, rather than through direct protein degradation (Zafeiropoulou et al. 2024). The persistently high mRNA level presumably reflects a feedback loop of the transcription process where the cell attempts to reestablish HIF-1 α levels in response to protein-damaging stress. This mechanism is frequently associated with bortezomib resistance in solid tumors (Zafeiropoulou et al. 2024).

This substantial difference between HIF-1 α transcription and HIF-1 α protein translation represents a critical observation of this study. Interestingly, while single-agent treatments and their combination were unable to reduce, and in some circumstances elevated, the transcription of HIF-1 α mRNA, Western blot analysis showed almost complete suppression of HIF-1 α proteins. Combining tioconazole with PX-478 or bortezomib significantly suppressed HIF-1 α protein levels ($p < 0.0001$) by approximately 0.25-fold (Fig. 5B). This disparity reveals a strong post-transcriptional mechanism, suggesting that tioconazole appears to aggravate translation stress, leading to HIF-1 α degradation despite persistent transcriptional activation. However, tioconazole, a selective ATG4B inhibitor, as a monotherapy, caused a notable increase in BNIP3 mRNA levels (3.5-fold), as shown in Fig. 4B. This autophagic spike likely reflects a cellular attempt to counteract ATG4B inhibition by triggering upstream mitophagy regulators, a survival mechanism, as mentioned in recent research on azole-derived autophagy inhibitors (Liu et al. 2018). This compensatory response highlights the limitations of employing tioconazole as monotherapy, as cells aggressively reorganize their signaling networks to preserve survival. Therefore, combining tioconazole with other agents is necessary to enhance cytotoxic effects and prevent adaptive survival pathways.

The synergy effect, migration ability, and protein expression data in this study demonstrate the advantages of the PX-478/tioconazole combination therapy. This combination showed broad-range synergy (scores > 10) according to the SynergyFinder analysis, whereas the synergy between bortezomib and tioconazole was limited to high concentrations (Fig. 2; Suppl. material 1: table S1). In addition, the functional impact of this molecular disturbance was demonstrated in the migration experiments. The hypoxic environment has been found to promote metastasis through the epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition (EMT) process (Yong et al. 2022; Jung et al. 2025). The findings of this study indicate that the combination therapies significantly reduced cell migration compared with the partial reduction when dosed with single agents (Fig. 3). This is consistent with recent studies indicating that the simultaneous inhibition of glycolysis (via HIF-1 α) and autophagy can deprive cancer cells of the bioenergetic supplies necessary for cytoskeletal restructuring and motility, as PX-478 has been demonstrated to interrupt these metabolic adaptations in solid cancers (Chu et al. 2020; Vidoni et al. 2023; Wang et al. 2024).

The molecular difference between the two combination approaches is further explained by the differential regulation of the Beclin-1 protein, a critical activator of autophagosome formation (Cao et al. 2024). Although tioconazole monotherapy significantly reduced Beclin-1 expression, consistent with autophagy dysfunction (Liu et al. 2018), adding lower and regular doses of bortezomib restored Beclin-1 levels above those in the hypoxic group (Fig. 5C). This elevation is likely due to bortezomib's pharmacological action; by blocking the 26S proteasome, bortezomib inhibits ubiquitin-dependent degradation of Beclin-1,

preserving the accumulation of autophagy-initiating proteins regardless of the presence of tioconazole (Sun et al. 2015). This sustained Beclin-1 expression in the bortezomib/tioconazole groups could trigger low-level autophagic activity that permits partial cell survival, explaining the narrow range of synergy observed for this combination. In contrast, the PX-478/tioconazole combination maintained the reduction in Beclin-1, indicating that upstream HIF-1 α blockade does not interfere with the disruptive effect of tioconazole (Fig. 5C). By preventing the proteasome-mediated buildup of Beclin-1, PX-478 treatment showed superiority over bortezomib in suppressing the autophagic marker Beclin-1 and consequently inhibiting the autophagic initiation complex, eventually driving the cells toward apoptosis.

The transition from autophagic survival to ultimate apoptosis is substantially regulated by the Bcl-2 protein family, which usually serves as an adaptive resistance area in breast cancer therapy (Alhoshani et al. 2020; Zhang et al. 2020; Palabiyik 2025). The regulation of the anti-apoptotic protein Bcl-2 is presumed to underlie the disparity in the synergy response. The data in this study demonstrated that monotherapy with PX-478, bortezomib, or tioconazole unexpectedly elevated Bcl-2 protein levels by 2- to 3-fold, with sustained expression of the autophagic marker ATG7 (Figs 4C, 5D). However, the combination of PX-478/tioconazole effectively removed this barrier, lowering Bcl-2 levels by 0.75-fold. In contrast, tioconazole mixed with different doses of bortezomib was unable to effectively decrease the Bcl-2 protein (Fig. 5D), possibly due to the inability to eliminate stress-induced survival signaling by the proteasome inhibitors (Zafeiropoulou et al. 2024). Recent literature demonstrates that autophagy inhibitors, including repurposed medicines such as tioconazole, can evade treatment-induced Bcl-2 overexpression by inhibiting autophagosome-lysosome fusion, resulting in a destructive accumulation of unresolved cellular stress (Palabiyik 2025). The superior efficacy of the PX-478 combination suggests that direct HIF-1 α blocking combined with autophagic disruption is substantially more effective at overcoming the apoptotic threshold than broad proteasome inhibition.

The substantial collapse of both Bcl-2 and HIF-1 α protein systems caused by the PX-478/tioconazole combination can be molecularly linked to the overexpression of the tumor suppressor PTEN. As this gene represents a master suppressor of the PI3K/Akt/mTOR signaling system, PTEN inhibition is effectively achieved by hypoxic breast carcinomas to sustain survival signaling, stabilize HIF-1 α , and prevent apoptosis (Luongo et al. 2019; Hassan and Aubeil 2025). In the current model, whereas hydralazine-induced hypoxia slightly suppressed PTEN expression, the combination of PX-478 and tioconazole resulted in a profound increase in PTEN levels (2.27-fold, $p < 0.01$) compared to moderate elevation (1.29-fold) with the bortezomib/tioconazole combination (Fig. 4D). The massive restoration of PTEN by PX-478/tioconazole treatment effectively eliminates PI3K/Akt-mediated survival signals, thereby removing the kinase activity necessary to stabilize

and upregulate anti-apoptotic proteins such as Bcl-2 under hypoxic stress, which leads to collapse in Bcl-2 and eventually cell death (Bu et al. 2021). Consequently, targeting HIF-1 α with PX-478 possesses a specific mechanistic advantage compared with bortezomib. In addition to its synergy effect with tioconazole in inducing autophagic and metabolic stress, PX-478 demonstrates a fundamental alteration in the cell's baseline survival function by restoring an important tumor suppressor. Collectively, these findings show that an appropriate combination of PX-478 and tioconazole specifically eliminates hypoxia-induced drug resistance by coordinating the restoration of PTEN and the profound collapse of the Bcl-2/HIF-1 α survival axis.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this research demonstrates that targeting the HIF-1 α /autophagy axis efficiently inhibits hypoxia-driven survival pathways in MCF-7 breast cancer cells. Combining the repurposed autophagy inhibitor tioconazole with the direct HIF-1 α blocker PX-478 produced profound synergistic cytotoxicity that exceeded the effect observed with the proteasome inhibitor bortezomib. The therapeutic advantage of the PX-478 combination is determined by an exclusive mechanism that restores the tumor suppressor PTEN, triggers a consequent collapse of the anti-apoptotic Bcl-2 response, enhances Beclin-1 suppression, and aggressively degrades HIF-1 α protein despite persistent mRNA signaling. These findings introduce a promising treatment approach of the PX-478/tioconazole combination for overcoming complex adaptive resistance pathways in hypoxic breast cancer. Future *in vivo* studies are necessary to confirm these results and investigate the translational potential of repurposing antifungal drugs such as tioconazole in cancer treatment.

Acknowledgements

The authors express their gratitude to the deanery of Mustansiriyah University-College of Pharmacy for allowing this work to be completed.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

Use of commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines: American Type Culture Collection (ATCC; Manassas, VA, USA).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

Z.A.: Working, validation, formal analysis, visualization, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing. I.S.A.: Supervision, investigation, methodology, writing—review and editing, validation, visualization.

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Data availability

The datasets used or analyzed during this study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request. Data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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journal of cancer research 7: 1198–1212. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28560067/>

Supplementary material 1

Suppl. table S1

Authors: Zakariya Al-Mashhadani

Data type: xlsx

Explanation note: This matrix table contains data of synergy score generated for the combination of PX-478 and Ticconazole by using the SynergyFinder web software.

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Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e190219.suppl1>

Supplementary material 2

Suppl. table S2

Authors: Zakariya Al-Mashhadani

Data type: xlsx

Explanation note: This matrix table contains data of synergy score generated for the combination of Bortezomib and Ticconazole by using the SynergyFinder web software.

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